

Teacher's Personality, Academic Stress, and Student Motivation Among Students in Tertiary Education in New Sinai School and Colleges

Christian Carlo T. Ibias

University of Perpetual Help System Laguna
C22-0781-213@uphsl.edu.ph

Article Details:

Received: 24 April 2026
Revised: 4 May 2026
Accepted: 15 May 2026
Published: 31 May 2026
Corresponding Email:
C22-0781-213@uphsl.edu.ph

Recommended Citation:

Ibias, C. C. T. (2026). Teacher's Personality, Academic Stress, and Student Motivation Among Students in Tertiary Education in New Sinai School and Colleges. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*. 1 (6), 403-413.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20474810>

Index Terms:

Teacher's personality, Academic stress, Student motivation, Tertiary education, Tertiary students

Abstract. Tertiary education is not just about obtaining a diploma; it is a journey that develops individuals into competent, well-rounded professionals that are capable of succeeding in real-world situations with confidence. Nevertheless, this path is not without its challenges. Using a descriptive- correlational research design, this study aims to identify students' preferred teacher personality, measure academic stress levels, and assess motivation. Also, determine the relationships among the variables among the tertiary students at New Sinai School and Colleges. The findings revealed that the respondents strongly preferred teachers with lenient personalities. The respondents also experienced a very high level of academic stress. Furthermore, the majority of the respondents demonstrated very high intrinsic motivation toward academic tasks. Based on these findings, an action plan was proposed to foster a supportive academic environment that promotes positive teacher personality traits, minimizes academic stress, and improves student motivation among tertiary students at New Sinai School and Colleges. The study concluded that students tend to prefer teachers who are patient and compassionate because these traits help them feel at ease and more actively involved in class discussions and activities. Students also experienced very high levels of stress whenever they were unable to achieve their personal standards. Moreover, students were strongly driven by personal achievement, emphasizing the importance of self-fulfillment in maintaining academic engagement. Findings further revealed that students who had a greater preference for their teachers' personalities were more likely to experience lower academic stress. Likewise, a stronger preference for teacher personality was linked to higher levels of student motivation. Therefore, the proposed action plan should be carried out to reinforce positive teacher personality traits, lessen academic stress, and improve student motivation.

Introduction

Tertiary education is more than just earning a degree—it's a life-changing experience that profoundly shapes individuals into skilled and well-rounded professionals who thrive in the real world with confidence. This period marks a transition as it leaves students' comfort zones to embrace independence and learn critical thinking and self-discovery. However, this journey isn't meaningful without its hurdles. The driving force given by motivation and the environment, especially the role played by teachers, is very prominent in keeping students motivated and engaged. A teacher's personality and encouragement can fuel a student's desire to learn or, unfortunately, create barriers. Each teacher has a different personality that may make or break students. However, university students often face challenges that contribute to their academic stress. Stress leads to mental problems, discomfort, and decreases in academic performance. Causal factors of students' stress include intense workloads, expectation pressures, and lack of support. Teachers are often associated with removing academic stress through creating meaningful environments, clear expectations, opportunities for constructive feedback, and open lines of communication. Teachers and students is key for managing stress to ensure a healthy, productive experience. Given the significant impact of academic stress on students' well-being, it becomes important to explore how motivation plays a role in managing this stress. Motivation can serve as a

powerful tool to help students navigate challenges, maintain focus, and persevere through difficult academic tasks. When students are motivated, students are more likely to adopt positive coping strategies, manage time effectively, and stay resilient in the face of stress.

Recent study by (Ridad and Sison, 2023) emphasizes that a teacher's personality greatly influences student learning and achievement. Students are motivated to learn when teachers are kind. Educators should create a secure, supportive environment in which students feel valued and respected. Promoting diversity and fostering positive relationships, teachers create an environment that nurtures students' emotional well-being. When students feel safe and comfortable, they are more likely to engage, explore new ideas, and experience personal growth.

The quality of professor-student interactions plays a significant role in shaping the level of academic stress experienced by students. University students commonly face a variety of stressors that contribute to their academic pressure. (Barbayannis et al., 2022) Educators have a vital responsibility in recognizing students who are experiencing academic stress and providing the support they need. Furthermore, (Bandara and Hettiwaththage, 2025) accentuate needs to cultivate both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to promote student achievement. It underscores the important role of educators and institutions in offering support, encouragement, and meaningful learning experiences that enable students to overcome challenges and attain their academic goals.

Despite the significance of teachers' personalities, academic stress, and student motivation in shaping academic success, no studies have examined these variables among students at New Sinai School and Colleges. Additionally, there is a lack of research investigating the correlation within this specific educational setting. While existing literature explores these factors individually or in other contexts, no studies have comprehensively analyzed the relationships among these variables at New Sinai School and colleges. Furthermore, both local and international studies remain limited. This gap emphasizes the need for further research to support students' academic success.

The primary goal is to identify students' preferred teacher personality, measure academic stress levels, and assess motivation among tertiary students at New Sinai School and Colleges. Also, it determined the relationships among the variables. Additionally, identified effective strategies to enhance teacher-student relationships to promote positive outcomes, including reducing academic stress levels and increasing student motivation, and provided insights for educational institutions and policymakers on the significance of teacher personality in shaping student experiences and outcomes within the academic context at New Sinai Colleges.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive correlational research design to examine teacher personality, student academic stress, and student motivation among tertiary students at New Sinai School and Colleges. This research strategy examined variable attributes with respect to relationship strength and direction, enabling researchers to study real-world interactions, formulate hypotheses, and inform teaching policies. Knowledge of these relationships enhances tertiary education and fosters a constructive learning environment conducive to student success.

Research Respondents

The respondents consisted of officially enrolled tertiary students at New Sinai School and Colleges, Sta. Rosa, Laguna, this Academic Year 2024-2025. Only empirical data from the respondents were collected for treatment and analysis. The respondents in this study were tertiary students from different programs being offered at New Sinai Schools and Colleges. The sample size was calculated using the Raosoft calculator, based on a total population of 133, with 99 respondents selected, using a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level.

Research Instruments

Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire that was validated and assessed by field experts. All feedback and suggested revisions from the validators were incorporated to ensure accuracy and quality. The researcher assessed the respondents' responses using a four-point Likert scale. Also, the questionnaire was subjected to a pilot test, where it was administered to thirty (30) respondents who met the same inclusion criteria as the actual participants but were not part of the final study population. Furthermore, a statistician examined the questionnaire to evaluate its internal consistency and overall reliability, and Cronbach's alpha was applied to measure the reliability of the study variables.

Instrumentation Validation

The adapted questionnaire underwent expert validation by field experts to ensure that the items retained reliability, validity, and appropriateness for the target population. Reliability testing was conducted using Cronbach's alpha, the results were as follows: both teacher personality and academic stress scored 0.99, while motivation scored 0.98. All of the variables were deemed excellent, indicating that the questionnaire's indicators were reliable. This process strengthened the credibility of the instrument while making it more accessible for school-based research.

Data Gathering Procedures

A systematic, step-by-step approach to ensure the collection of valuable information while upholding the confidentiality of all participants. Initially, an authorization letter was sent to each program to permit the researchers to collect data in line with the study's requirements and conduct the research. Following approval of the letter, participant selection was based on predetermined criteria. Subsequently, the distribution of survey questionnaires was carried out in alignment with the research objectives and in accordance with informed consent requirements. Survey was conducted in private and secure environments. Throughout the process, rest reassured all participants that all responses and personal information would be kept strictly confidential and used solely for research purposes.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The weighted mean, were computed to identify students' preferred teacher personality, measure academic stress levels, and assess motivation To examine the relationships among the three variables, Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was employed as the primary inferential statistical tool. Using this dual threshold allowed for a more comprehensive interpretation of the findings, ensuring that the results were not only statistically significant but also practically meaningful.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study are presented according to the research questions:

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. I prefer a teacher who enforces strict discipline in the classroom.	3.45	0.576	Highly Preferred	5
2. I learn better when there are clear rules and expectations set by the teacher	3.58	0.517	Highly Preferred	2
3. I feel challenged to perform well in class when the teacher consistently takes control to maintain order.	3.54	0.594	Highly Preferred	4
4. I appreciate teachers who are confident and assertive in their teaching style.	3.67	0.495	Highly Preferred	1
5. A firm teacher helps me stay focused on my studies.	3.55	0.576	Highly Preferred	3
Composite WM	3.56	0.489	Highly Preferred	

Table 1. Preferred Teachers' Personality in terms of Authoritative Personality

All indicators were interpreted as highly preferred. Among the indicators, Indicator 4, the preference for confident and assertive teachers, had the highest weighted mean of 3.67 (SD = 0.495). This was followed by Indicator 2, ranking 2nd, clear rules and expectations set for better learning, gaining a weighted mean of 3.58 (SD = 0.517). Also next is Indicator 5, ranked 3rd; a firm teaching approach had a weighted mean of 3.55 (SD = 0.576). This is closely followed by Indicator 3, Preference is for teachers who maintain strict discipline in the classroom, which received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean of 3.45 (SD = 0.576) and was ranked fourth. Lastly, teachers who enforce strict discipline in the classroom ranked fifth with a weighted mean of 3.45 and a standard deviation of 0.576.

Overall, with a composite weighted mean of 3.56 and standard deviation of 0.489, the findings indicate that respondents highly prefer teachers of Authoritative personality who demonstrate confidence, assertiveness, and clear guidance in the classroom, while strict discipline, although valued, is relatively less prioritized.

According to Syafrizal (2024), confidence in teaching allows educators to establish authority effectively, maintain classroom order, and deliver lessons with clarity and purpose. Demonstrating assertiveness alongside guidance, teachers

create a structured and supportive learning environment in which students feel focused, motivated, and encouraged to perform at their best.

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. I like a teacher who is patient and lenient with student errors.	3.72	0.453	Highly Preferred	3.5
2. It is easier for me to learn from a teacher who is calm and easygoing	3.72	0.453	Highly Preferred	3.5
3. A patient and kind teacher makes me feel more comfortable engaging in class.	3.77	0.424	Highly Preferred	1
4. I enjoy when teachers are considerate with deadlines and assignments.	3.75	0.437	Highly Preferred	2
5. I feel closer to teachers who treat students as friends.	3.56	0.539	Highly Preferred	5
Composite WM	3.70	0.401	Highly Preferred	

Table 2. Preferred Teachers' Personality in terms of Lenient Personality

All indicators were interpreted as highly preferred. Among the indicators, Indicator 3, a patient and kind teacher that makes me feel more comfortable engaging in class, had the highest weighted mean of 3.77 (SD = 0.424), ranking first. This was followed by Indicator 4, enjoyment when teachers are considerate with deadlines and assignments, which ranked second with a weighted mean of 3.75 (SD = 0.437). Indicators 1 and 2, liking teachers who are patient and lenient with student errors and ease of learning from a teacher who is calm and easygoing, both received a weighted mean of 3.72 (SD = 0.453) and shared the third rank (3.5). Lastly, Indicator 5, feeling closer to teachers who treat students as friends, had the lowest rank with a weighted mean of 3.56 (SD = 0.539).

Overall, the findings indicate that respondents highly prefer teachers with Lenient personality, who demonstrate patience, kindness, and consideration, creating a supportive and comfortable classroom environment.

When teachers demonstrate kindness, warmth, and consideration, students are more likely to participate actively, feel secure in expressing themselves, and have positive learning experiences in the classroom (Sun, 2023).

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. I like classes where teachers employ innovative teaching styles.	3.66	0.477	Highly Preferred	4
2. I prefer teachers who apply technology or multimedia components in their classes.	3.61	0.531	Highly Preferred	5
3. Teachers who think outside the box make learning more interesting.	3.68	0.512	Highly Preferred	3
4. I enjoy teachers who add fun activities or games to present topics.	3.68	0.491	Highly Preferred	3
5. I learn better from teachers who continuously bring new ideas to the classroom.	3.72	0.453	Highly Preferred	1
Composite WM	3.67	0.431	Highly Preferred	

Table 3. Preferred Teachers' Personality in terms of Innovative Personality

All indicators were interpreted as highly preferred. Among the indicators, Indicator 5, feeling closer to teachers who treat students as friends, had the highest weighted mean of 3.72 (SD = 0.453), ranking first. This suggests that respondents highly value teachers who foster positive relationships and approachability alongside innovative practices. Indicators 3 and 4, a patient and kind teacher makes students feel more comfortable engaging in class and enjoyment when teachers are considerate with deadlines and assignments, both received a weighted mean of 3.68 (SD = 0.512 and 0.491, respectively) and shared the third rank. Indicator 1, liking a teacher who is patient and lenient with student errors, obtained a weighted mean of 3.66 (SD = 0.477) and ranked fourth, while Indicator 2, ease of learning from a teacher who is calm and easygoing, received the lowest rank with a weighted mean of 3.61 (SD = 0.531).

The composited weighted mean of 3.67 indicates that respondents highly prefer teachers with innovative personality, who are approachable and have strong student-teacher relationships. A friendly, non-threatening classroom atmosphere encourages students to express ideas, ask questions, and participate without fear of judgment. This relational closeness strengthens student-teacher rapport, increases engagement and fosters a supportive, collaborative learning environment (Hendrian & Kurniawati, 2024).

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. I like teachers who adapt their teaching style to students' needs.	3.69	0.466	Highly Preferred	4
2. A good teacher adjusts their method when students are having difficulty.	3.72	0.453	Highly Preferred	1
3. I prefer it when teachers are receptive to student input and make changes.	3.65	0.501	Highly Preferred	5
4. I like a teacher who can handle multiple learning styles within a single class.	3.69	0.466	Highly Preferred	4
5. I feel supported when a teacher adjusts to classroom situations that arise unexpectedly, calmly.	3.71	0.457	Highly Preferred	2
Composite WM	3.69	0.432	Highly Preferred	

Table 4. Preferred Teachers' Personality in terms of Adaptive Personality

All indicators were interpreted as highly preferred. Among the indicators, Indicator 2, a good teacher that adjusts their method when students are having difficulty, had the highest weighted mean of 3.72 (SD = 0.453), ranking first. This suggests that respondents highly value teachers who can modify their approach to support students' learning challenges. Indicator 5, feeling supported when a teacher adjusts to the classroom, situations that arise unexpectedly, calmly, ranked second with a weighted mean of 3.71 (SD = 0.457). Indicators 1 and 4, liking teachers who adapt their teaching style to students' needs and handling multiple learning styles within a single class, both obtained a weighted mean of 3.69 (SD = 0.466) and shared the fourth rank. Lastly, Indicator 3, preference for teachers who are receptive to student input and make changes, received the lowest rank with a weighted mean of 3.65 (SD = 0.501).

The overall composite weighted mean of 3.69 with a standard deviation of 0.432 confirms a very high preference for adaptive teaching practices. The findings indicate that respondents highly prefer teachers who are flexible, responsive, and able to adjust to both student needs and unexpected classroom situations.

When teachers adjust their strategies, such as simplifying explanations, offering more examples, or using different methods, they help students better understand complex concepts. This flexibility demonstrates attention to students' academic needs, supports an inclusive classroom, and improves comprehension. As a result, students are more confident, engaged, and likely to achieve stronger academic outcomes (Ridad & Sison, 2023).

Scale	Domains	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
Personality	Authoritative	3.56	0.489	Highly Preferred	4
	Lenient	3.70	0.401	Highly Preferred	1
	Innovative	3.67	0.431	Highly Preferred	3
	Adaptive	3.69	0.432	Highly Preferred	2
OVERALL		3.65	0.395	Highly Preferred	

Table 5. Summary of the Overall Preferred Teachers' Personality

Among the domains, Lenient Personality obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.70 and SD = 0.401. This was followed by adaptive personality with a weighted mean of 3.69 and SD = 0.432. Next is Innovative Personality with a weighted mean of 3.67 and SD = 0.431. Lastly, Authoritative Personality obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.56, SD = 0.489. All domains were interpreted as very high.

The overall weighted mean is 3.65, SD = 0.395, which falls under the interpretation of "highly preferred." This indicates that students strongly prefer teachers who possess a combination of positive personality traits. Although all domains were rated highly preferred. The highest-ranked domain, lenient personality, suggests that students particularly value patience, kindness, and understanding in their teachers.

Research by Syafrizal (2024) found that discipline balanced with warmth and flexibility enhances student engagement and fosters a positive learning climate. Similarly, studies on teacher-student relationships highlight that patience and kindness contribute significantly to students' academic motivation, participation, and overall satisfaction with learning.

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. Motivation comes from parents' high expectations, used as encouragement to do the best academically.	3.18	0.873	Very High	8
2. Teacher's high standards are met with effort to improve and grow in learning.	3.42	0.640	Very High	2
3. Setbacks are accepted as part of the process and used to strengthen performance.	3.47	0.595	Very High	1
4. Confidence is being built in managing expectations and focusing on steady progress rather than fear of disappointing others.	3.34	0.745	Very High	4
5. Better strategies are being developed to manage workload when feeling overwhelmed by assignments.	3.27	0.767	Very High	5
6. Ability to handle multiple subjects and responsibilities is improving step by step.	3.38	0.666	Very High	3
7. Balance is being created to include rest and leisure alongside schoolwork.	3.00	0.833	Very High	12
8. Efforts are being made to balance academics, extracurricular activities, and personal life in a healthier way.	3.19	0.724	Very High	10
9. Action is being taken earlier to reduce procrastination when tasks feel overwhelming.	3.14	0.783	Very High	11
10. Self-confidence is being strengthened to reduce fear of judgment over grades.	3.19	0.867	Very High	10
11. Focus is shifting toward personal growth rather than stress from peer comparison.	3.18	0.861	Very High	8
12. Appreciation for individual academic journeys is growing instead of constant comparison with others.	3.21	0.895	Very High	6
Composite WM	3.25	0.638	Very High	

Table 6. Summary of the Level of Academic Stress

All indicators were interpreted as very high with a composite weighted mean of 3.25 and a standard deviation of 0.638, suggesting that respondents generally experience a very high level of academic stress. Among the indicators, the highest-ranked source of stress was learning from setbacks (Indicator 3), with a weighted mean of 3.47 (SD = 0.595). This was followed by the teacher's high standards being met with effort to improve and grow in learning. Indicator 2, which ranked second with a weighted mean of 3.42 (SD = 0.640), and Indicator 6, handling multiple subjects, ranked third with a weighted mean of 3.38 (SD = 0.666). confidence in expectations (WM = 3.34, SD = 0.745, Rank 4); better strategies are being developed to manage workload when feeling overwhelmed by assignments. (WM = 3.27, SD = 0.767, Rank 5). Indicator 7, related to balanced lifestyle, ranked lower but was still within the very low-stress range. The lowest-ranked source of stress was schoolwork interfering with my time to relax or engage in leisure activities (WM = 3.00, SD = 0.833, Rank 12).

The composite weighted mean of 3.25 indicates that overall, students experience very high academic stress. This is justified by the highest-ranked indicator, failing to meet personal standards.

Feeling stressed when personal standards are not met is a common experience among students who set high expectations for themselves. Academic life often requires consistent performance, discipline, and achievement. When personal goals are not achieved, feelings of disappointment, frustration, and self-doubt may arise. This stress is not only caused by external pressures from teachers or parents but also by internal expectations that students impose on themselves (Gottschlich & Atapour, 2024).

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
I feel excited when I work on tasks that interest me.	3.73	0.448	Very High	3.5
I take pride in doing my best, even without external rewards	3.70	0.483	Very High	6
I enjoy learning new things simply for the sake of learning.	3.70	0.462	Very High	6
I feel fulfilled when I overcome a challenge on my own.	3.81	0.396	Very High	1
My curiosity drives me to explore new ideas.	3.76	0.431	Very High	2
I find joy in completing tasks that reflect my personal growth.	3.73	0.448	Very High	3.5
Composite WM	3.74	0.403	Very High	

Table 7. Level of Motivation in terms of Intrinsic Motivation

The highest-ranked indicator is the feeling of fulfillment in overcoming challenges independently, with a weighted mean of 3.81. This is followed by curiosity in exploring new ideas with a weighted mean of 3.76. Next are excitement in working on interesting tasks and completing tasks that reflect personal growth, both with a weighted mean of 3.73. The lowest-ranked indicators are take pride in doing best without expecting reward and enjoying learning new things for the sake of learning, each with a weighted mean of 3.70.

The data revealed the composite weighted mean of 3.74, which was interpreted as "very high," indicating that students possess a very high level of intrinsic motivation. This high overall result shows that students derive strong fulfillment from overcoming challenges independently. Personal accomplishment and self-driven success play a crucial role in sustaining students' intrinsic motivation in their academic pursuits. When students achieve goals through their own efforts, they experience a sense of fulfillment that reinforces their desire to continue learning. This internal satisfaction becomes a powerful driving force, encouraging them to persist even when faced with challenges or difficulties (Kamberi, 2025).

Indicators	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
When my efforts are recognized by others, I feel encouraged to work	3.70	0.462	Very High	4
I stay motivated when I know my work leads to tangible rewards.	3.64	0.562	Very High	6
I enjoy receiving praise for a job well done.	3.68	0.512	Very High	5
The opportunities for advancement and success motivate me to work well	3.72	0.453	Very High	2.5
I feel more focused when my performance is acknowledged.	3.72	0.496	Very High	2.5
I'm motivated when I know my contributions are valued by others.	3.74	0.465	Very High	1
Composite WM	3.70	0.438	Very High	

Table 8. Level of Motivation in terms of Extrinsic Motivation

All indicators were interpreted as very high. Among the indicators, "They're motivated when they know that their contributions are valued by others", obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.74 (SD = 0.465), suggesting that recognition and appreciation are the most influential factors in motivating respondents. This was followed by "The opportunities for advancement and success motivate me to work well" and "They feel more focused when my performance is acknowledged", both with a weighted mean of 3.72 (SD = 0.453 and 10.49, respectively), indicating that acknowledgment and future opportunities also play a significant role in enhancing motivation. Next, "When their efforts are recognized by others, they feel encouraged to work", ranked closely with a weighted mean of 3.70 (SD = 0.462), followed by "They enjoy receiving praise for a job well done", with a weighted mean of 3.68 (SD = 0.512). Lastly, "They stay motivated when I know my work leads to tangible rewards" obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.64 (SD = 0.562), although it was still interpreted as very high.

Overall, the findings indicate that respondents are highly motivated by external rewards such as recognition, praise, acknowledgment, and opportunities for success with a composite weighted mean of 3.70 and a standard deviation of 0.438, indicating that external factors strongly influence the respondents' motivation.

Ismail (2023) found that students who receive external messages of approval from teachers, parents, and friends are more likely to continue pursuing more difficult academic pursuits. Their study highlights that praise and acknowledgment, as positive reinforcers, can significantly increase motivation and engagement.

Scale	Domains	WM	SD	Interpretation	Rank
Motivation	Intrinsic	3.74	0.403	Very High	1
	Extrinsic	3.70	0.438	Very High	2
OVERALL		3.72	0.394	Very High	

Table 9. Summary of the overall Level of Motivation

Among the domains, intrinsic motivation obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.74, SD = 0.403, interpreted as "very high," followed by extrinsic motivation with a weighted mean of 3.70, SD = 0.438, also interpreted as "very high."

The overall weighted mean is 3.72, SD = 0.394, which is interpreted as "very high." The study revealed that students are very highly motivated when they feel fulfilled in overcoming a challenge on their own, which highlights that personal satisfaction and accomplishment play a key role in sustaining students' overall motivation and engagement in academic tasks.

Students who willingly take on challenges independently demonstrate that personal satisfaction and a strong sense of accomplishment are essential factors in sustaining their overall motivation. As they successfully navigate these challenges, they develop greater confidence in their abilities, which further reinforces their engagement in academic tasks. Ultimately, this sense of self-fulfillment not only enhances their persistence but also contributes to deeper learning and continuous academic involvement (Basileo et al., 2024).

Independent	Dependent	Pearson's r ^a	p-value	Decision	Interpretation ^b
Authoritative	Academic Stress	.147 (very weak)	.147	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Lenient		.274 (weak)	.006	Reject H ₀	Significant
Innovative		.209 (weak)	.037	Reject H ₀	Significant
Adaptive		.272 (weak)	.006	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 10. Relationship between the Respondents' Preferred Teachers' Personality and their Level of Academic Stress

Using Pearson's correlation, among the domains, lenient personality shows a weak positive correlation with academic stress (r = 0.274, p = 0.006), which is significant, indicating that students' preference for lenient teachers is associated with variations in stress levels. Similarly, adaptive personality has a weak positive correlation (r = 0.272, p = 0.006), also significant, suggesting that students who prefer adaptive teachers may experience differences in academic stress.

Innovative personality shows a weak positive correlation as well ($r = 0.209$, $p = 0.037$), which is significant, implying a slight association between preference for innovative teachers and stress levels. On the other hand, authoritative personality has a very weak positive correlation with academic stress ($r = 0.147$, $p = 0.147$), which is not significant, indicating that students' preference for authoritative teachers does not meaningfully relate to their level of stress.

Overall, the findings indicate that authoritative personality does not significantly influence academic stress. Lenient, innovative, and adaptive teacher traits have a weak but statistically significant relationship with students' academic stress. This implies that students' stress levels are slightly affected by how teachers approach flexibility, creativity, and consideration in teaching.

Students' academic experiences are greatly influenced by their teachers. Students' academic stress levels are strongly influenced by teacher personality traits, including empathy, openness, adaptability, and leadership style (Urien and Enoje, 2024).

Independent	Dependent	Pearson's r^a	p -value	Decision	Interpretation ^b
Preferred Personality	Motivation	.610 (strong)	.000	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 11. Relationship between the Respondents' Preferred Teachers' Personality and their Level of Motivation

Using Pearson's correlation, the results show a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.610$, $p = 0.000$), which is significant, indicating that students exhibit higher motivation when they are taught by their preferred teacher.

Students' motivation and involvement in the learning process are greatly influenced by the personality of the teacher. Students are more likely to feel supported and understood when teachers display qualities that match their preferences, such as confidence, approachability, empathy, and good communication (Ridad & Sison, 2023).

Independent	Dependent	Pearson's r^a	p -value	Decision	Interpretation ^b
Academic stress	Motivation	.216 (weak)	.041	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 12. Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Academic Stress and their Level of Motivation

Using Pearson's correlation, results show that academic stress has a weak positive correlation with motivation ($r = 0.216$, $p = 0.041$), which is significant, indicating that lower levels of stress are slightly associated with higher levels of motivation.

When students experience manageable stress, they are better able to organize their time, set achievable goals, and remain committed to their academic tasks. Reduced stress allows students to approach learning with greater confidence and energy, which naturally fosters motivation (Garbenis & Kaffemaniene, 2025).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study revealed that students tend to favor teachers who are patient and approachable, as these characteristics help them feel at ease and more actively involved in classroom activities. Students also reported experiencing very high levels of stress when they were unable to meet their own expectations. At the same time, they were strongly motivated by a sense of personal achievement, underscoring the importance of self-fulfillment in maintaining academic engagement. The findings further revealed that students who had a stronger preference for their teachers' personality traits were more likely to experience lower levels of academic stress. Moreover, a higher preference for teacher personality was associated with increased student motivation.

Drawing from these results, the proposed action plan for tertiary students at New Sinai School and Colleges is based on the study's findings, which show that positive teacher personality traits, reduced academic stress, and sustained motivation significantly shape students' learning experiences and academic engagement. Teachers who are supportive, approachable, and empathetic contribute to a positive classroom environment by building strong relationships with students and encouraging active participation in class. Excessive academic stress can adversely affect students' motivation, academic performance, and overall well-being. In response, it is essential to implement programs and

interventions that enhance teachers' interpersonal qualities while equipping students with effective strategies for managing academic demands. By addressing these areas, the institution can cultivate a more supportive and motivating learning environment that enriches students' educational experiences, strengthens their motivation, and promotes academic success.

Acknowledgement

The researcher extends heartfelt gratitude to Dr. Remedios M. Dela Rosa, adviser, for her unwavering guidance, expertise, and encouragement throughout the completion of this study. Sincere appreciation is also given to the Dean of the College, the panelists of the paper, statistician, editor and the office of Graduate School for their invaluable support and approval that made this research possible.

Special thanks to the respondents of this research, the tertiary students of New Sinai School and Colleges from different programs, for their time, cooperation, and willingness to participate. Their contributions were crucial to the successful completion of this research.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific funding from public, commercial, or nonprofit organizations. It was carried out independently by the authors as part of their academic requirements, with institutional assistance limited to academic guidance and supervision.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work presented in this study. The research was conducted independently, and all analyses, interpretations, and recommendations were developed solely for academic purposes.

Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated and analyzed during this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. In addition, aggregated data tables, statistical outputs, and other supporting materials used in the analysis may be accessed for academic and research purposes.

References

- Ananada, Ananada. (2025). The Influence of Teacher Personality on Student Motivation and Learning Outcomes: A Systematic Review from an Economics of Education Perspective. *PERFECT EDUCATION FAIRY*, 3. 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.56442/pef.v3i1.1063>
- Bandara, K. M. N. T. K., & Hettiwaththage, R. C. (2025). The Interplay of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation in Academic Achievement: A Comprehensive Review. *Sri Lanka Journal of Social Work*, 9(2), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljsw.v9i2.24>
- Barbayannis, G., Bandari, M., Zheng, X., Baquerizo, H., Pecor, K. W., & Ming, X. (2022). Academic Stress and Mental Well-Being in College Students: Correlations, Affected Groups, and COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13(886344). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.886344>
- Basileo, Lindsey & Otto, Barbara & Lyons, Merewyn & Vannini, Natalie & Toth, Michael. (2024). The role of self-efficacy, motivation, and perceived support of students' basic psychological needs in academic achievement. *Frontiers in Education*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1385442>
- Deng Y, Cherian J, Khan NUN, Kumari K, Sial MS, Comite U, Gavurova B, Popp J. Family and Academic Stress and Their Impact on Students' Depression Level and Academic Performance. *Front Psychiatry*. 2022 Jun 16;13:869337. PMID: 35782431; PMCID: PMC9243415. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.869337>
- Garbenis, S., & Kaffemaniene, I. (2025). Developing Traits of Self-Confidence and Intrinsic Motivation in Students with Severe Special Educational Needs in Physical Education Lessons. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(11), 1449. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15111449>
- Gottschlich, D., & Atapour, N. (2024). Experiences of Academic Stress and Coping Mechanisms in High-Achieving Students. *KMAN Counseling and Psychology Nexus*, 2(2), 19-26. <https://doi.org/10.61838/kman.psychnexus.2.2.4>
- Hawthorne, H. (2021, November 17). Types of Motivation in Education | Intrinsic & Extrinsic Effects. *The Hub | High Speed Training*. <https://www.highspeedtraining.co.uk/hub/motivation-in-education/>

- Hendrian, Noviena & Kurniawati, Lemmuela. (2024). A correlational study on teacher-student relationships and students' engagement in EFL classes. *Cambodian Journal of Educational and Social Sciences (CJESS)*, 1. 53-74. <https://doi.org/10.69496/cjess.v1i2.31>
- Indeed Editorial Team. (2021, March 18). 8 Types of Motivation to Achieve Your Goals | Indeed.com. [www.indeed.com](https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/types-of-motivation). <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/types-of-motivation>
- Ismail, I. A. (2023). Using positive reinforcement to increase student engagement in using positive reinforcement to increase student engagement in the classroom the classroom. <https://red.mnstate.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1885&context=thesis>
- Kamberi, M. (2025). The types of intrinsic motivation as predictors of academic achievement: the mediating role of deep learning strategy. *Cogent Education*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2025.2482482>
- Ridad, L. J., & Sison, M. O. (2023). TEACHER'S RELATED-FACTORS, LEARNING STYLE AND BEHAVIORAL ENGAGEMENT OF RADIOLOGIC TECHNOLOGY STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITY OF PERPETUAL HELP-DR. JOSE G. TAMAYO MEDICAL UNIVERSITY, BINAN, LAGUNA. *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences*, 54(3), S33-S33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmir.2023.06.120>
- Sun Y. The Effect of Teacher Caring Behavior and Teacher Praise on Students' Engagement in EFL Classrooms. *Front Psychol.* 2021 Sep 14;12:746871. PMID: 34594287; PMCID: PMC8478015. <https://doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2021.746871>
- Syafrizal. (2024). The Influence Of Teachers Confidence On Teaching And Learning Process In School. *JOLADU: Journal of Language Education*, 2(3), 150-159. <https://doi.org/10.58738/joladu.v2i3.369>
- Urien, J., & Courage Enoje, S. (2024). Students Perception of Teachers' Personality and Its Impact on Learning Outcomes in Delta State. *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management (IJHSSM)*, 4, 1367-1377. https://ijhssm.org/issue_dcp/Students%20Perception%20of%20Teachers%20%20Personality%20and%20Its%20Impact%20on%20Learning%20Outcomes%20in%20Delta%20State.pdf

Appendices

This study does not include appendices or supplementary documents.